

Reducing Our Travel Footprint

Background Research Document

FOR THE FACULTY OF SOCIAL SCIENCES
uOttawa

uOttawa

REDUCING OUR TRAVEL FOOTPRINT
Background Research Document for the Faculty of Social Sciences,
University of Ottawa

Sara M. Bechtold, Ida-Maria Chvostek, and [Ryan Katz-Rosene](#)

Presented to the Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Ottawa

Published online: May 2024

Suggested citation: Bechtold, S.M., Chvostek, I-M., and Katz-Rosene, R. (2024). Reducing Our Travel Footprint: Background Research Document, Prepared for the Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Ottawa. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11055180>

Authorship contribution statement:

Sara M. Bechtold (PhD Candidate, uOttawa): Conceptualization, Travel Decision Tree Tool, Editing & Review

Ida-Maria Chvostek (Phd Student, uOttawa): Conceptualization, Decision Tree Visuals

Ryan Katz-Rosene (Associate Professor, uOttawa): Conceptualization, Calculations, Supervision

For questions and comments, please send an email to: rkatzros@uottawa.ca

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REDUCING OUR TRAVEL FOOTPRINT

A Travel Decision Tree for the Faculty of Social Sciences, uOttawa

Introduction to this Background Research Document

This document provides details and evidence underlying the six main sections of the *Travel Decision Tree* tool that we have jointly prepared for the University of Ottawa's Faculty of Social Sciences, titled **To Fly or Not to Fly? Moving Towards Climate-Friendly Scholarly Travel**. The *Travel Decision Tree* tool is intended as a succinct and visually appealing communication aid, and this supplementary background document enables any interested readers to delve further into the underlying data.

SECTION 1: WE NEED TO FIND A BETTER PATH

This first section of the *Travel Decision Tree* explains *why* travel-related carbon footprints matter, considering in particular the significant climate impacts associated with flying. It contextualizes the climate emergency in order to explain why we need to move towards climate-friendly travel practices in academia. We situate the climate crisis in relation to Canada and Ottawa specifically.

1.1 Why our travel footprint matters

Canada is among the top ten greenhouse gas (GHG) emitters in the world (see *Figure 1*). Further, its *per capita* cumulative emissions since 1850 have ranked either 1st or 2nd (depending on how historical populations are calculated) in national responsibility to climate change (see *Figure 2 on the next page*). Such data represents the present and historic responsibility - at both state and citizen levels - to climate change today.

For the global average temperature to stay below a safety threshold of 1.5°C per the IPCC, large-scale reductions in GHG emissions must occur. For its part, Canadian per-capita GHG emissions would have to decline from **13.5 tCO₂e** (tons of CO₂ equivalent) **per year in 2016** to **2.1 tCO₂e per year by 2050**. While many reductions can come from changes in the way energy, food, and transport services are produced and supplied, life-style emissions - that is, emissions resulting from everyday decisions about personal and household consumption - can also play a key role.

Figure 1: Top ten GHG emitters in the world. (Adapted from [WRI](#), 2023)

Rank	Country	Cumulative Emissions PER POPULATION (2021) – tCO2	Rank	Country	Cumulative Emissions PER CAPITA
1	Canada	1751	1	New Zealand	5764
2	United States	1547	2	Canada	4772
3	Estonia	1394	3	Australia	4013
4	Australia	1388	4	United States	3820

Figure 2: Top Four CO2 emitting countries on a historical per capita basis, 1850-2021. (Adapted from *Carbonbrief*, 2021)

While any lifestyle changes carrying a smaller carbon footprint constitute a step in the right direction, some changes will be significantly more impactful than others. For example, on a national level (see *Figure 3*), transportation emerges as a key site where individuals and households are able to reduce our emissions. The transport sector currently serves as the second largest emitting sector (and this only counts ‘tailpipe’ emissions; additional emissions associated with the transport supply chain - such as

fuel production and road and infrastructure construction, and so on - are counted in other sectors). Importantly, emissions from ‘international’ travel are not included in Canada’s National GHG Inventory as below; this would add roughly another 15Mt CO2 per year to Canadians’ annual transport emissions.

Figure 3: Breakdown of Canada’s GHG emissions by IPCC sector, 2021. (Adapted from *Government of Canada* data, 2021)

At the level of the individual, avoiding air travel constitutes a high-impact action that is relatively easy to undertake. This is especially so for frequent fliers (those who fly more than 6 flights per year). Unlike emissions directly related to our ability to survive, such as food and warmth, flying is generally not considered a “need”. In fact, a recent study asking university students about their flying habits found that nearly half of all flights taken were not seen as “important” by the travelers themselves. In

2010, academic and climate scientist Peter Kalmus calculated that his flights' carbon footprint accounted for two thirds of his entire personal climate impact. Kalmus - a Canadian atmospheric scientist at Caltech - shared his findings, which prompted him to stop flying and to call for a shift in travel decision-making at policy and systems-levels.

The University of Ottawa's Air Travel Footprint. The uOttawa Office of Sustainability conducted a review of university-related travel patterns, using receipts and credit card information over a 5-year period (note: the data assumes travel back and forth and does not factor in multiple flights or lay-overs). The results of this research found that considering the 30,066 total trips by uOttawa between 2015-2020 (reaching 15,640,130kg), and where train trips emit 16 times fewer emissions than flying, switching to train travel from a plane or car could avoid over 5,000 kilograms of CO2 per year along the Windsor/Quebec corridor. See **Appendix B** for an infographic of the study's results.

The University of Ottawa's Climate Mitigation Goals. uOttawa has made a climate pledge: "Our goal is to become a carbon neutral campus by the year 2040 and reduce direct greenhouse gas emissions (scope 1 emissions) by 100%." Further, within the uOttawa family of faculties, the Faculty of Social Sciences (FSS) has shared their Vision on sustainability: "Make progress in environmental sustainability by strengthening engagement within our FSS community and fostering positive change locally and around the world. Advance and share our research knowledge in the field of Social Sciences and humanities to help understand environmental problems and develop solutions."

Traditionally, academic norms have included carbon intensive practices such as traveling for conferences and workshops, or visiting distant locations for field work. However, as data continues to reveal the associated costs on climate, we are critically reexamining the pros, cons and options of scholarly travel.

1.2 A snapshot of the climate emergency

The climate costs of national economic activity and household-level habits are contributing to an increasingly urgent global situation. Climate change is reshaping the world as we know it, rapidly increasing global surface temperatures - and our vocabulary is adapting to keep up. The first "climate emergency" was declared in Darebin, Australia in 2016, but it was global youth protests that later made the phrase mainstream - including the Oxford Dictionary's declaring it word-of-the-year in 2019. Resultantly, in Canada, the Government first declared a climate emergency the same year; former Environment and Climate Change Minister Catherine McKenna called on the House to "declare that Canada is in a national climate emergency which requires... that Canada commit to meeting its national emissions target under the Paris Agreement and to making deeper reductions in line with the Agreement's

objective of holding global warming below two degrees Celsius and pursuing efforts to keep global warming below 1.5 degrees Celsius.”

Canadians now belong to the more than 1 billion people living under a climate emergency declaration. In Canada, 37 academic institutions have also declared a climate emergency as part of a joint effort involving more than 1000 institutions around the world. While uOttawa is not one of the signatories, the University has still made it clear that climate change poses a wide range of risks requiring substantial efforts in terms of education, information, and engagement, with the aim of reducing our school’s carbon footprint (read the latest uOttawa Climate Change Report here). Before focusing on specific sustainable actions such as changing travel practices, we will start by looking closer at some of the changes that rising temperatures will bring about in Canada and Ottawa.

Climate change poses increased physical risks. Experts generally consider physical climate risk along eight key hazards: coastal flood, fluvial flood, extreme heat, extreme cold, tropical cyclone, wildfire, water stress and drought. They are able to track these hazards’ impact using climate models, geospatial data, ownership mapping and vulnerability pathways - and the intelligence data, though key to climate resilience, is harrowing. For example, in the case of flooding, research reveals how climate change is intensifying the planetary water cycle and causing more extreme weather events. From a Canadian perspective, this is concerning given its many flood-prone areas. In just the past few years, the capital city of Ottawa for example has experienced severe flooding on multiple occasions, both from extreme rainfall events and spring snowmelt. Floods have large-scale negative impacts on economic functions, with damages counting in the billions - and preparing a city like Ottawa to handle more extreme weather events will require large scale infrastructure investments. This goes beyond updating stormwater and sewer systems to consider ways in which excess water can be better absorbed. Non-permeable surfaces such as roads, rooftops, and parking lots all inhibit the water cycle and leave cities like Ottawa more vulnerable to floods and erosion.

Canada is already experiencing extreme and compound events - simultaneously facing heatwaves, droughts, and wildfires among other physical hazards. Just as one area sees more rain, other areas experience drought; individuals and communities across Canada are already experiencing more frequent as well as geographically and temporally more significant droughts. Climate change is also affecting food production, including price fluctuations hitting both producers and consumers as well as crop loss. For instance, the 2021 heat dome damaged British Columbia’s fruit harvest - reducing yields and losing \$17 million in revenue. Associated increased financial burdens particularly impact individuals and households with lower socioeconomic status. Further, along with drier and warmer weather also comes the risk of forest fires - with Canada’s circumboreal forest zone being particularly

susceptible to increased fire activity. Canada's 2023 wildfire season recorded the most hectares burned in the recent historical record. This included the destruction of Lytton, British Columbia - a wildfire event that killed two and displaced another 1000 citizens. Natural Resources Canada expects the annual area of wildfire burn to increase on average alongside global warming.

Climate change and health. Along with physical risk to our environment, social and financial systems, climate change also threatens our health. For example, floods bring about both short- and long-term physical health risks in terms of safety and disease; further, they are associated with mental health issues like the trauma that comes with losing one's house or livelihood. In the case of droughts, we face associated respiratory issues and reduced drinking water quality. And a final example is forest fires, which have serious health implications as biomass emissions in the form of particulate matter (PM) and volatile organic compounds (VOCs) affect the quality of the air we breathe. Recent research observing course grades of undergraduate students at uOttawa shows that the effect of air pollution negatively impacts cognitive productivity even at lower concentrations.

In sum, this is just some of the research underpinning our understanding of the physical risks and health implications of climate change. Experts continue to unpack this, as well as associated negative emotional impacts like our sense of security and continuity within this changing world, as well.

1.3 The need to move to more sustainable travel practices

Considering the climate emergency, its impacts on our earth, social and economic systems, and how we as nations and individuals contribute to climate change, we set the stage for a shift to more sustainable travel practices. We confront the challenge of unsustainable transportation via three main approaches:

- 1) We can make the most emissions-intensive transport modes climate-friendly;
- 2) We can switch from more emissions-intensive to less emissions-intensive modes;
- 3) We can avoid traveling altogether (virtual conferencing and research).

Our Travel Decision Tree tool helps us consider the benefits and limitations of all three of these approaches. First, however, we explain how aviation itself impacts the climate, as it is often the most carbon-intensive mode of *longhaul* travel - and has a disproportionate impact on our particular University's intercity travel carbon footprint.

Aviation has a net warming influence. Presently, the UN Secretary-General's High-Level Advisory Group on Sustainable Transport does not classify aviation as a 'sustainable' mode of travel as it incurs a significant warming influence on the planet. Aviation impacts the climate primarily through two main mechanisms: first, the consumption of fossil-based fuels; and second, the formation of contrails. Contrails are the white

streaks coming off high-flying jet airplanes; they form when water vapor condenses and freezes around small particles (aerosols) in aircraft exhaust. As shown in *Figure 4*, the burning of fuels emits Carbon Dioxide (CO₂) and Nitrogen Oxides (NO_x) - the former of which is a Greenhouse Gas, and the latter of which is implicated indirectly in changes to the atmospheric concentration of GHGs. The wide array of atmospheric reactions associated with aviation fuel combustion up in the atmosphere have both warming and cooling influences on the climate, but the warming influence far outweighs the cooling influence - such that the global aviation sector contributed to up to 4.9% of anthropogenic “radiative forcing” in 2005 (that is, the warming influence that humans had on the Earth’s system that year). A more recent assessment found that aviation’s net warming influence in 2011 was 3.5% of anthropogenic effective radiative forcing. As this is just one human activity that is only used by a very small fraction of the world’s population in a given year, we begin to see how aviation thereby has an outsized climate impact.

Figure 4: How Aviation Changes the Atmosphere and Influences Surface Temperatures. (Adapted from Lee et al., 2009)

SECTION 2: TECHNOLOGY ALONE WON'T GET US THERE

This second section of the Travel Decision Tree shows how technological innovations in aviation are indeed making a difference and offer the promise of a more sustainable aviation sector in the future. However, relying on these technological innovations on their own is unlikely to be sufficient in getting us truly climate-friendly long-distance transport.

There are three main ‘buckets’ of technological innovations that help to reduce the climate impact of aviation: 1) cleaner fuels; 2) aircraft innovations; and 3) operational improvements. All three of these have *already* played a significant role in reducing the climate footprint of the global aviation sector; however, historically, increases in air transport demand have outweighed the efficiency gains obtained from these innovations, leaving an ever-growing climate footprint in aviation. The following three sections review these ‘buckets’ in closer detail.

2.1 Sustainable aviation fuels: classes and their proposed reductions

Conventional jet fuel (also known as kerosene) is typically a hydrocarbon produced from refined petroleum. When burned, these fuels emit CO₂ and other pollutants which impact the climate - either directly or indirectly, as shown in *Figure 5* above. Different classes of sustainable aviation fuels (SAFs) have been proposed to reduce the climate impact of aviation fuel combustion.

One main class of SAF is biofuels. In theory, biofuels combustion is “carbon neutral” because the CO₂ emitted is equivalent to the CO₂ which was removed from the atmosphere through photosynthesis and taken up into the biological materials used as a feedstock for the biofuel production. Of course, the production of biofuels itself uses energy, and so the net climate impact of a given biofuel will depend on which types of biological material is used and what type of processes are used in production. There is also a potential carbon opportunity cost from biofuels usage in cases where the feedstock is specifically produced on agricultural land (since that land could have instead been used to produce food). Still, one of the most promising areas of biofuels is when the feedstock is derived from waste residues (for instance, from the forestry sector, municipal waste, or agricultural waste). As shown in the Life Cycle Analysis in *Figure 6* below, only one type of SAF is truly carbon ‘negative’ - that made by municipal solid waste containing biological content. A recent study found this is because: a) municipal waste which contains biological material will often emit CH₄ to the atmosphere, and so using it as fuel ensures that the emitted GHG (CO₂) is ‘used’ rather than wasted, and has a lower warming potential; and b) plastic within municipal solid waste is very stable and thus serves as a sort of carbon sink (it is thus better to leave it in landfill rather than burn it).

Another class of SAFs is “synthfuels” (or sometimes called ‘electrofuels’). Synthfuels are synthetically produced ‘hydrocarbons’ which use atmospheric CO₂ as a feedstock.

Thus, as with biofuels, they are technically carbon neutral when the emitted CO₂ from combustion merely returns to the atmosphere from whence it came; and, like biofuels, the net climate impact of synthfuels depends largely on the energy processes used in their production. *Figure 5* below shows that electrofuels produced with renewable energy are indeed significantly less damaging than conventional petroleum-based jet fuel; however, it is still above zero (thus not climate neutral). Meanwhile, electrofuels produced on the standard electrical grid emit more than conventional petroleum-based jet fuels.

Figure 5: Assessing the Sustainability Implications of Alternative Aviation Fuels. (Reproduced with permission from Pavlenko and Searle, 2021)

Presently, the use of SAFs in the aviation industry is limited, despite considerable demand and the more than 375 million liters of SAF produced in 2022. This still amounts to a mere fraction of total aviation fuel production and consumption. Nevertheless, as *Figure 6* below notes, the share of global aviation consumption to be taken up by SAFs is expected to grow considerably over the coming years - potentially reaching around 4.5% of global demand in 2030. Of course, one danger is that while this will reduce the carbon intensity of aviation fuel burn, it will still not bring emissions down to zero (though, based on new research considering the climate influence of reductions in conventional jet fuel burn, this could still be consistent with a safe climate future for aviation).

Figure 6: Sustainable Aviation Fuels Demand Projections. (Adapted with approximations from from *Bloomberg NEF, 2022*)

2.2 The potential for efficiency gains from aircraft innovations

Aside from making the fuels more climate friendly, one can significantly cut down on fuel burn (and thus reduce the climatic impact of aviation) by making the aircraft more efficient - or even by making aircraft that do not require fuel at all. The aircraft industry points out that fuel efficiency improvements from improvements to aircraft design have been consistent since the beginning of aviation, and proposes that these efficiency gains (which have thus far improved the fuel efficiency of aviation by about 80% over the last 50 years) will continue into the future as the sector aims for Net Zero. These innovations will at first comprise better aerodynamic designs, lower weight materials (like composites instead of aluminum), and better engines, before integrating electric aviation (first through hybrid-electric aircraft, and then possibly through fully electric aircraft).

Presently, electric aircraft are considered to be an unlikely option for long-haul flights (further than 600 nautical miles, or 1100km), and switching over all of the world’s flights of under this distance to all-electric aircraft would consume an enormous amount of electricity (equivalent to about 0.6%-1.7% of worldwide electricity consumption in 2015). Nevertheless, electric aircraft would not only eliminate direct CO2 emissions, but also the emissions on non-CO2 air pollutants which also contribute to global warming in conventional fuel-burning aircraft. Meanwhile, *hybrid*-electric planes may enable an aircraft to travel longer distances by combining electric batteries and fuel together. When combined with new airframe and body designs, hybrid- electric aircraft could support CO2 emissions reductions of up to

40%. As Figure 7 below shows, the fuel efficiency of contemporary aircraft is orders of magnitude better than older aircraft.

of magnitude better than older aircraft. The problem, however, is that demand growth for aviation is outpacing these fuel efficiency improvements.

Figure 7: Fuel efficiency of commercial aircraft over time. (Adapted with approximations from Quiggin, 2023)

2.3 Optimization through operational improvements

Operational improvements, such as enhanced air traffic control systems and the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) based flight paths, are also able to help reduce the climate footprint of aviation - primarily by allowing a flight to burn less fuel. Advanced technologies, such as next-generation air traffic management systems, allow for dynamic rerouting based on real-time data and environmental considerations. By optimizing flight trajectories, aircraft can avoid congestion, adverse weather conditions, and other factors that contribute to increased fuel burn and emissions. Additionally, precise coordination between air traffic controllers and pilots can enable smoother descents and climbs, reducing the need for excessive fuel usage. As the European Aviation Safety Agency reports, a considerable amount of ‘excess CO2’ is generated during all stages of a given flight (between gates) - emissions which would not otherwise be generated with more efficient taxiing, take off, ascent and descent and routing protocols (see *Figure 8 below*).

In addition to avoiding CO2 emissions, rerouting can support climate-friendlier aviation by helping an aircraft to avoid contrails. A pilot project run by Google using AI found that aircraft were able to avoid contrail formation by 54% by rerouting flights based on large datasets and contrail-forming conditions. The downside to the project was that - while successfully reducing contrails - the planes ended up using *more fuel* to adjust their routes. So the non-CO2 impacts were reduced with AI-based air traffic controls, but at a cost of 2% more fuel burn (and presumably, 2% more CO2). As this ‘trade-off’ suggests, the extent of emissions reductions that can be achieved by operational improvements is perhaps limited. And, even if ‘excess CO2’ could be

Figure 8: Breakdown of gate-to-gate excess CO2 emissions for an average flight in Europe. (Adapted from EASA, 2022)

entirely removed, and contrails reduced significantly, there would still be the CO2 emissions from fuel burned.

In summary, the technological innovations in the aviation sector are indeed supporting a reduction of the carbon intensity of flight. That said, growing demand for aviation has historically outpaced these gains - and demand is likely to continue growing now that the sector is making a post-pandemic recovery. Further, there are often spinoff second-order climate impacts associated with these technological innovations, which in some ways erodes some of the climatic benefits of these green aviation technologies.

SECTION 3: ...NEITHER WILL OFFSETS

The third section of the Travel Decision Tree demonstrates that amidst an increase in the use of carbon offsets across industries, including aviation - and amidst an uptick in policies formulated specifically to support offsets as a sustainability tool - reliance upon them as a catchall solution remains problematic.

3.1 Carbon offsets: a brief overview

A carbon offset is a credit for emissions reductions given to one party that can be sold to another party to compensate for its own emissions. Measured in tonnes of carbon dioxide-equivalent (CO₂e), offset units act as a transferable financial instrument to help mitigate the environmental harm caused by emissions. In international aviation, emissions generated by air travel can be offset by purchasing these units via projects or programs outside the sector.

Broadly, there are two types of offsets: removal and avoidance. *Removal* offsets pull carbon out of the atmosphere, for example via reforestation or Direct Air Capture, while *avoidance* offsets prevent the release of carbon - for example by preventing deforestation. Offsets projects fall under several categories, including: forestry and land use, renewable energy, blue carbon, waste management, transportation, agriculture land management, households and community devices, methane capture, biomass sequestration, industrial energy efficiency, and others.

Offsets offer a particularly attractive option for hard-to-abate industries like aviation. Despite improvements in fuel efficiency and other decarbonization efforts, the aviation sector's absolute growth of emissions far outpaces its gains. Therefore, offsets are playing a role in the early stages of the aviation industry's path to decarbonization.

3.2 CORSIA: the UN's plan to offset aviation emissions

While the Paris Agreement accounts for *domestic* aviation emissions through its national pledges mechanism, *international* aviation emissions are covered by the United Nations' International Civil Aviation Group (ICAO). In 2016, the ICAO implemented a Carbon Offsetting and Reduction Scheme for International Aviation (CORSIA) to address the sector's rapidly rising emissions - allowing airlines to offset any growth above its 2019 levels of CO₂ emissions. 192 countries signed onto CORSIA in support of the low-carbon growth of the international aviation sector. As its pilot phase closed at the end of 2023, its first (2024-26) and second (2027-35) phases came into effect - with voluntary participation ending in phase two, meaning most international flights will be subject to offsetting requirements.

To determine the required offsets, flight operators track the fuel use of each trip and calculate their CO₂ emissions; and, since January 2019, CORSIA has required those with emissions greater than 10,000 tonnes of CO₂ per year to report annually. (This

and other information is summarized in a useful [fact sheet](#) on CORSIA created by the International Air Transport Association (IATA). The IATA, headquartered in Montreal, is a trade association for airlines, representing 82% of the world’s major carriers as of 2020). These annual emissions reports are verified by accredited, third-party verification bodies. Accordingly, operators consult the ICAO Council’s approved list of eligible emissions that can be used for compliance. Project certifications vary depending on institutional context, though a comprehensive list of offsets programs’ eligibility criteria can be found [here](#).

According to the ICAO, CORSIA (and CORSIA eligible fuels) will be responsible for the significant majority of estimated international aviation net CO₂ emissions reductions, as compared to other decarbonization measures (see *Figure 9*).

Figure 9: Contribution of CORSIA for reducing international aviation net CO₂ emissions. (Reproduced with permission from [ICAO](#), 2022)

However, although there is a system of global governance aiming to reduce the climate footprint of aviation through offsets, a following subsection (3.4) highlights current data on its variable success.

3.3 Canada’s Tri-Council policy on the use of carbon offsets

Within the Canadian context, a Tri-Council of three agencies was formed to jointly administer grant funding in support of high-quality research across disciplines; it is the primary mechanism through which the Canadian government supports research and training at post-secondary institutions. The Tri-Council consists of The Canadian Institutes of Health Research (CIHR), the Natural Sciences and Engineering Research

Council of Canada ([NSERC](#)), and the Social Science and Humanities Research Council of Canada ([SSHRC](#)).

Grant recipients and administering institutions are governed by the [Tri-Agency Financial Administration Guide](#). Per Canada's [Greening Government Strategy](#), travel expenses may include the cost of carbon offset credits; accordingly updated on April 1st, 2023, the **Tri-agency statement on carbon offsets** reads:

The Government of Canada recognizes the importance of decreasing greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions in order to reduce the negative impacts of climate change on Canada and globally. In this context, the agencies encourage grant recipients to consider the necessity of grant-funded travel, and to reduce this when possible. When grant-funded travel is necessary for the research activities, the agencies encourage grant recipients to use lower-carbon forms of transportation to help reduce GHG emissions. The agencies consider carbon offset costs (related to air travel or other transportation) to be an appropriate use of grant funds for research/activities that are aligned with the principles and directives of the Tri-agency Guide on Financial Administration.

As the ensuing paragraph illustrates, while carbon offset costs are indeed eligible as a reimbursable research expense, there is additional thought warranted on whether or not researchers *should* purchase carbon offsets and if so, what *kind* of offsets best meet the goals of the researcher.

3.4 The current, fraught stage of carbon offsetting

The efficacy of offsets, in aviation and beyond, remains a subject of research and debate. Although they are one in a necessary toolkit of greenhouse gas reduction options, there persists a level of uncertainty around the quality, credibility and nature of offsets projects. As the UK-based [Committee on Climate Change](#) recently published: “high-integrity carbon credits... can play a small but important role in supporting the transition to Net Zero... but... Government must put in place stronger guidance, regulation and standards to ensure purchase of carbon credits is not used as a substitute for direct business emissions reduction, and to improve the integrity and transparency of carbon credits. In the absence of these measures, there is a real risk that voluntary carbon markets slow progress towards Net Zero.”

Within aviation, emerging research indicates that most carbon offsets eligible under the sector's offset scheme (CORSIA) only “have minor climate integrity.” The same study also challenged CORSIA's future potential: “it is highly questionable whether there is enough potential supply of offsets to ensure such high integrity, indicating that carbon offsetting should be considered as a transitory measure only.” So although CORSIA requires airlines to purchase offsets for international flights, several critical issues - including the following - persist:

- *Permanence*. Offsets projects may not permanently trap greenhouse gasses, and may not do so on a timeline that matches the lifespan of the gasses in the atmosphere. Some GHGs can last for hundreds of years - yet certain offsets projects risk the potential release of stored carbon back into the atmosphere. Projects particularly prone to this risk are forest-related offsets, where wildfires, logging, or changes in forestry or land use policy could “reverse” the offset. For such projects, risk assessment considers a period of 100 years. (Wonzy et al., 2022; Chagas et al., 2019; Schneider & Wissner, 2022)
- *Additionality*. Ensuring that the reductions claimed by an offset are “in addition to” what would have otherwise already been reduced without the offset purchase presents a core challenge for offsets policy. Assessing whether an offset project truly caused emissions reductions that would not have happened otherwise, however, is complex and often subjective. If the market is flooded with credits from projects lacking additionality, it can diminish the intended environmental impact and efficacy of offsetting as a tool for mitigating climate change. As the Energy and Climate Intelligence Unit’s March 2021 paper states, “Studies show that offsets do not always provide fully additional effort, and reliance on them may present risks to effective mitigation.” Further, as additionality requirements vary across jurisdictions and have a high degree of baseline uncertainty, quantifying the net carbon reductions from offsets is challenging. (Broekhoff et al., 2020; West et al., 2020; Wozny et al., 2022)
- *Leakage*. Activity-shifting leakage happens when a reduction effort from one sector or geographical location results in an increase in emissions elsewhere. This can happen when carbon market and economic shifts impact demand and offset activities, but also when regulatory stringency lacks uniformity across jurisdictions. Less than comprehensive international agreements and regulatory frameworks risk simply shifting rather than reducing net emissions; however, even with robust and comprehensive frameworks, research has found that the act of measuring leakage with a high degree of precision remains costly and inconclusive.

A critical commonality among these and other challenges with offsets is *credibility*. Inflated impact claims and questionable accounting, the potential for scams, loopholes and gaming the system, and the broader issue of a social license to operate - that is, the ethics of ostensibly allowing offset buyers to keep polluting - can negatively impact both the perception and efficacy of offsets. Addressing these and other challenges associated with offsets is critical to ensure that intended emissions reductions are achieved without unintended negative impacts elsewhere.

3.5 The potential for better, next generation carbon offsets

Despite the ongoing and not insignificant challenges with offsets, their apparent entrenchment in both policy and practice perhaps warrants an optimistic eye toward

the potential for betterment. Accordingly, this chapter concludes by considering the concept of ‘next generation offsets’ - or the potential for developing promising innovations and advancing offset strategies.

Next generation offsets include more robust and advanced tracking and monitoring, more evolved nature-based solutions’ management, and more efficient and effective technological developments. Tracking and monitoring technologies are fast-evolving as artificial intelligence platforms commercialize, and remote-sensing and satellite monitoring capacities continue to grow. The oversight of nature-based options like afforestation and reforestation - among the most difficult sequestration options to quantify - is improving as strategic understanding and management of these carbon sinks matures. And in terms of innovative technologies, evidence shows high interest - and investment - in Carbon Capture, Utilization and Sequestration (CCUS). CCUS is an umbrella acronym for a range of potentially promising emissions reductions technologies. These include direct air capture, in which CO₂ is directly captured from the atmosphere; repurposing emissions into for instance synthetic jet fuels or cement; geological sequestration, where CO₂ is captured from industrial processes and injected into geological formations underground for long-term storage; and, of particular application in Canada and the US, the use of CO₂ to pressurize oil flow for enhanced oil recovery (EOR). As of 2021, CCUS development held potential for 130 million tonnes per annum of capture capacity.

Within the aviation sector, point-source capture and carbon sequestration present the most cost-effective solution for decarbonizing the aviation industry; and, as promising research by Becattini et al. (2021) indicates, it is cost competitive with business-as-usual already today. Further, COP 28 highlighted the importance of carbon offsetting to compensate for the as-yet unavoidable emissions generated by air travel.

In sum, offsets may well be elemental in addressing emissions and climate change. However, their current troubled state indicates they cannot be a substitute for significant emissions cuts. The aviation sector’s exploration of supplementary strategies - such as adopting more fuel-efficient technologies, investing in sustainable aviation fuels, and exploring next generation offset innovations to reduce the overall carbon footprint of air travel - is paramount.

SECTION 4: THERE ARE MORE SUSTAINABLE ALTERNATIVES...

In this section we cover the likely carbon footprints associated with travel from the University of Ottawa to other parts of the world, given the best available research as contextualized by real world scenarios. It is important to note, however, that variations in travel options *within* modes and in different contexts can result in different climate impacts. For instance: Traveling in a full plane where all seats are occupied results in far less emissions *per passenger* than traveling in a plane that is only half full (the assumption being that less total flights would be required if the planes were filled to capacity). This ‘load factor’ issue also relates to Business Class travel; Traveling Business Class roughly doubles the climate impact because the seats take up about twice as much space. In another example, taking an ‘electrified’ form of transport (like an Electric Vehicle) in a jurisdiction where the electricity is generated from fossil fuels will result in a higher climate impact than if the grid is low carbon. *Generally speaking - in global terms - the least polluting form of intercity public transportation is rail transport, followed by coach bus, personal vehicle, and then aviation* (see *Figure 10*; the green dots denote averages for *intercity* travel).

Figure 10: Global Average (and Range) GHG Intensities by Travel Mode. (Reproduced with permission from IEA, 2019)

However, as the yellow ranges in the figure show, there is a great variation between least and most polluting forms of each transport mode. As we will read below, Canada’s rail transport *outside* of the Quebec Windsor Corridor is *especially* carbon intensive today. Electrified transport is ‘greener’ in jurisdictions

like Quebec and Ontario than it is in other provinces where the grid features fossil fuel production. This is why we break this up Section into three subsections: i) travel within the Quebec City-Windsor Corridor (QWC); ii) domestic travel *outside* of the QWC; and iii) international and overseas travel - we use specific travel destination examples to help illustrate the *most realistic* climate impact of travel from Ottawa

and back. **Appendix A** contains a list of relevant emissions factors that we used for this particular analysis.

4.1 Travel within the Quebec-Windsor Corridor

The ‘transport corridor’ between Windsor and Quebec features many of Canada’s most populated cities, and multiple transport infrastructures. The most likely forms of travel within the corridor for research are: flying (West Jet, Air Canada, and Porter); personal vehicle; train (VIA Rail); or coach bus (offered by Orléans Express or Flixbus to Montreal and Toronto). Based on the relevant emissions factors analyzed for this study, we determined the average GHG emissions per passenger, based on a range of transport possibilities. As *Figure 11* shows, the climate impact of vehicle traffic depends significantly on two main factors: First, whether the vehicle is an electric vehicle (EV) or an International Combustion Engine vehicle (ICE); and second, whether the vehicle is carrying 1 passenger, 2 passengers, or is full.

Figure 11: Average Emissions Factors by transport mode for travel within the Quebec City - Windsor Corridor or to Regional US Destinations (New York, Boston, Chicago), kg CO2e per passenger km. (Katz-Rosene, 2024)

Note: Plug-in Hybrid Vehicles (PHEV) are considered ‘EVs’ in the analysis above. Non-plug in hybrids are considered ICE cars. ‘Large cars’ includes small trucks, SUVs and minivans.

Based on these emissions factors, we can model the **most likely** carbon footprint per passenger of a return trip to Montreal or Toronto - two of the most likely destinations within the QWC from Ottawa, as seen in *Figures 12 and 13*:

Figure 12: Total carbon footprint per passenger RETURN TRIP (kg CO₂e), Ottawa-Montreal.
(Katz-Rosene, 2024)

Figure 13: Total Carbon Footprint per passenger RETURN TRIP (kg CO₂e), Ottawa - Toronto.
(Katz-Rosene, 2024)

These figures tell us that *generally speaking*, for travel within the corridor, the lowest climate impact form of travel is an electric vehicle, and the highest climate impact is an internal combustion engine vehicle with only one occupant (a solo driver). Generally speaking, flying is one of the most carbon intensive forms of transport in the corridor as well. Interestingly, for the Ottawa-Montreal trip, flying is the second most carbon-intensive form of transport; yet for the Ottawa-Toronto trip, flying is the third most carbon-intensive form of transport. This is because the flight distance between Ottawa and Toronto (353km) is nearly 100km shorter than the typical

highway distance along Highway 401 (450km). *One general takeaway is thus that the further the distance traveled, the more of a distance reduction advantage aviation offers.*

4.2 Domestic travel within North America outside of the Quebec-Windsor Corridor

As noted above, rail travel *outside* of the QWC is especially Carbon-intensive, and recent research specifically examining the Canadian long distance travel market has found that the train is actually more carbon intensive than flying. This is for three main reasons: First, long-distance trains in Canada and most of the US are powered by diesel; Second, long-distance trains typically have very low occupancy (low load factors) in North America; and third, in a full trip context, trains often travel further than airplanes - which have much shorter distances to travel thanks to direct flight paths. For *Figure 14*, we do not include single-occupancy vehicles, on the assumption that it would not be practical (or safe) to drive solo long distances. The emissions factor for long haul aviation is smaller than that of short haul aviation. This is partly because a smaller portion of the flight is spent climbing to altitude, which is the most energy-intensive portion of a flight.

Figure 14: Average emissions factors by transport mode for long-distance intercity in North America outside of the Quebec-Windsor corridor, kg CO2e per passenger km. (Katz-Rosene, 2024)

As a result of these changes in mode, a flight across Canada (using an average of short haul and long haul emissions factors) is typically going to generate less CO2 per passenger than taking VIA's existing Rail services (see *Figures 15 and 16*):

Figure 15: Total Carbon Footprint per passenger RETURN TRIP (kg CO₂e), Ottawa- Halifax, Nova Scotia. (Katz-Rosene, 2024)

Figure 16: Total Carbon Footprint per passenger RETURN TRIP (kg CO₂e), Ottawa- Vancouver. (Katz-Rosene, 2024)

4.3 International travel outside the US and Canada

For International and overseas travel from Ottawa, the only viable travel option at present is flying. As we can see in *Figure 17*, the further the distance, the higher the carbon footprint of international travel. A return trip to Amsterdam, for instance, would incur a carbon footprint of 2335 kg CO₂e. This is almost 19X the flight carbon footprint of traveling to Toronto by plane, and almost 100X more carbon intensive than traveling to Toronto and back by VIA Rail. To limit our carbon footprint from research and scholarly activities, then, we can a) choose the most carbon-efficient

mode of transport available for a given trip; and b) choose to limit (or altogether avoid) longer distance trips to only necessary travel.

Figure 17: Return Trip Carbon Footprint per Passenger (kg CO₂e), Ottawa to Select International Destinations. (Katz-Rosene, 2024)

To sum up, here are some Rules of Thumb for University of Ottawa researchers seeking to reduce their travel carbon footprint:

1. *Carpooling*: Adding more passengers reduces the carbon footprint by reducing the number of vehicles required
2. *Train travel*: Globally, rail is the most efficient mode of transport. However, within Canada, rail travel is relatively high impact, especially for trans-continental travel.
3. *Quebec Windsor Corridor*: With regional travel, rail and coach bus are the lowest Carbon mass transportation options.
4. *Electric Vehicles (EVs)*: EVs have a much lower carbon footprint than Combustion-Engine vehicles. However, in jurisdictions with carbon-intensive Electricity Grids, EVs have less of a comparable weaker advantage.
5. *Flying*: Avoiding a single round trip flight (by attending a conference virtually, or biannually, for instance), can save an enormous amount of carbon from entering the atmosphere.
6. Use our Travel Decision Tree tool on the next page to help think through your best options!

SECTION 5: ...BUT WE NEED TO TAKE THE NEXT STEPS: *The Travel Decision Tree*

Before booking a flight, consider the questions in this *Travel Decision Tree* tool - keeping in mind the climate impact of flying and and your research objectives:

Figure 18: A Travel Decision Tree Tool (Bechtold et al, 2024)

Note: please see the original Travel Decision Tree document for functional hyperlinks.

SECTION 6: JOIN WITH OTHERS!

Climate change urgently requires that we reduce our carbon footprint. While this goal can be achieved in various ways, avoiding air travel constitutes a high-impact action that is relatively easy to undertake. By going through the steps outlined in the *Travel Decision Tree* prior to committing to research-related travel, you could save as much as 1.6tCO₂e simply by cutting out one transatlantic flight. While this number might seem like a drop in the bucket, it becomes significant when considering that our remaining *lifetime* CO₂ budget per person is now limited to 29.8 tCO₂ - if we are to meet global warming goals.

Similarly, the collective impact of a group of people critically examining their travel behaviors matters. For example, uOttawa's academic staff of around 1,200 people could avoid close to 2,000 tCO₂e annually by skipping one longer flight each. By cascading this basic ethos to our nearly 40,000 undergraduate and 8,000 graduate students, even more significant emissions avoidance could be made.

We understand that part of this experience might not come easy, and change takes time. Fortunately, staying local does not mean giving up the pleasures that come from engaging and collaborating with other scholars. We encourage you to use available technology to keep in touch with peers within your field, and to organize with scholars from around the world who are similarly interested in reducing their travel footprints. For professors, we encourage you to talk to your students about this topic - including sharing how your own travel decisions may have shifted - and consider embedding it within curriculums wherever it might help. Normalizing the dialogue about alternatives to travel can challenge not only the way we perceive traveling in general but also traditional travel as a component of an academic career.

For further reading, we recommend the following resources: the Academic Flying Less Movement; the Flying Less in Academia Resource Guide; the Flying Less project and the We Stay on the Ground movement.

6.1. Integrate your flight footprint into your research plans

The amount we travel by air is not uniformly distributed within academic settings. Instead, most air travel is accredited to a small minority of frequent flyers; senior scholars often being responsible for a significantly higher footprint. Therefore, it may help to start evaluating every trip from an environmental as well as an equity perspective. For example, if your travel habits put you in the group of hypermobile academics, you might consider letting an early career scientist that you know attend a workshop or conference in your place. While attending a conference might not drastically change your career path, sharing their work could be what is required to launch the career of someone who is just starting their academic journey.

Similarly, if you are organizing a conference, you might consider ways in which you can reimagine attendance. In a paper published in *Nature* in 2020, Klöwer et al. looked closer at ways in which conference travel could be made more sustainable. They found that by going fully virtual in 2020, the attendance at the annual meeting of the European Geosciences Union (EGU) increased from its usual 16,000 attendees to 26,000. In addition to making conferences more accessible to scholars with limited

funds, or with family commitments that prevent long-haul travel, changes like this also come with huge emissions savings. By going fully virtual, a large conference such as the one arranged annually by the American Geophysical Union (AGU) could reduce emissions by 99.9% (See Figure 19).

Figure 19: Different models of attending the annual AGU, and their respective reductions in emissions, compared to in-person attendance with long-haul aviation being accepted as the norm. (Adapted from Klöwer et al., 2020)

Other ways of reducing emissions include relocating conferences to locations that are more accessible or implementing a “hub model” where coordinated multi-local events are arranged. In both cases, this would reduce the need for long-haul flights significantly. Finally, conferences can also be altered to take place on a biannual basis - cutting associated emissions in half. Conferences that have already shifted to this model include the AGU’s Ocean Sciences Meeting as well as The International Conference on Ecolinguistics. In addition, following a petition to replace their three in-person meetings a year, the American Philosophical Association (APA) has created a committee to look into the possibility of shifting to a 2+1 model, making one of their meetings fully virtual.

While these sorts of changes might seem limiting to some, the fact is that annual, year-after-year, in-person attendance at conferences is not automatically associated with academic success. Instead, as shown by Wynes et al. (2019), there seems to be no relationship between academic productivity and flying. And ultimately - especially if you work within the field of climate change and sustainability - flying less could have the positive side effects of increasing your credibility and inspiring change.

6.2. Taking it further...

Finally, we fully acknowledge that reducing our footprint is not an effort that should be placed solely on the individual. Following [Jacobson et al.'s \(2020\) Three Spheres of Transformation](#) framework, change also depends on technology as well as political, social, and cultural systems (See [Figure 20](#)).

Figure 20: *The Three Spheres of Transformation, which are all required to interact with each other if we are to change the norms around flying. (Reproduced with permission from [Jacobson et al., 2020](#))*

As sustainable transitions expert Peter Newell and colleagues [have explained](#), personal actions on climate change do not exist in a vacuum. They are an integral part of the broader spiral of sustainability, often by drawing interconnections with actions at larger scales: “Personal action can also be linked to other forms of collective activities, social practices, political influence and engagement with the wider world.” Through this research, we have aimed to underscore the significance of critically assessing our roles within the scholarly community in driving climate change mitigation, particularly through conscientious travel decisions. Moving forward, it is imperative that we continue to foster an ethos of responsibility and innovation, ensuring that our individual contributions resonate across the global canvas of environmental action.

APPENDIX A: Emissions Factors Used in this Analysis

				QWC+	Relevance Domestic /NA	Intl/ /NA	overseas*
VIA Rail Toronto to Ottawa (From: https://www.viarail.ca/en/plan-your-trip/book-travel/compare-train-and-car)							
One way trip [445km]		kg CO2e per SEAT	kg CO2e/pKM				
Train (based on 5-yr average fuel consumption per passenger km data)		43	0.096	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Aviation (based on 5-yr DEFRA average) & IPCC Radiative Factor		133	0.296	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Vehicle (1 occupant) (based on 5-yr NRCAN Energy Use Database average car fuel use)		87	0.194	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
VIA Rail Montreal to Ottawa (From: https://www.viarail.ca/en/plan-your-trip/book-travel/compare-train-and-car)							
One way trip [198km]		kg CO2e per SEAT	kg CO2e/pKM				
Train (based on 5-yr average fuel consumption per passenger km data)		18	0.091	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Aviation (based on 5-yr DEFRA average) & IPCC Radiative Factor		56	0.283	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Vehicle (1 occupant) (based on 5-yr NRCAN Energy Use Database average car fuel use)		38	0.192	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
North American Transport Emissions Factors from Liu et al. http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.trd.2016.08.027							
Operation-related component of intercity travel in the USA	grams CO2/pKM	kg CO2/pKM	kg CO2e/pKM				
SUV 1 passenger	310	0.31	0.31	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Sedan 1 passenger	230	0.23	0.23	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
SUV 2 passengers	156	0.156	0.156	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Sedan 2 passengers	113	0.113	0.113	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Smaller (Regional) Jet - assumed 80% occupancy	167	0.167	0.167	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Larger (Single Aisle) Aircraft - assumed 80% occupancy	133	0.133	0.133	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
SUV 4 passengers	77	0.077	0.077	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Sedan 4 passengers	58	0.058	0.058	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Bus - assumed 50% occupancy	39	0.039	0.039	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Railway Association of Canada's 'Intercity Passenger GHG Emissions Intensity							
		kg CO2/pKM	kg CO2e/pKM				
Intercity Passenger Rail in Canada: Average of 2017-2019, includes load factor changes		0.0947	0.095	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Average Emissions Factors from Bigazzi et al. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2019.03.172							
	grams CO2/pKM	kg CO2/pKM	kg CO2e/pKM				
Intercity Rail (US) average from 32 Studies	96	0.096	0.096	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Air (US) average from 32 Studies	104	0.104	0.104	Yes	Yes	No	No
Emissions Factors from Kageson 2009 https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/environmental-aspects-of-inter-city-passenger-transport_5kmmnc9dlcbs.pdf							
	grams CO2/pKM	kg CO2/pKM	kg CO2e/pKM				
Average of Internal Combustion and Electric Cars, European Grid, 2 passengers	98.8	0.0988	0.099	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Intercity Coach Bus assuming 55% occupancy	19.1	0.0191	0.019	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Intercity "Fast trains" (not high-speed) assuming 65% occupancy and Electric Traction	14.6	0.0146	0.015	No	No	Yes	Yes
Shorthaul Aircraft	117.2	0.1172	0.117	Yes	Yes	No	No
Atmosfair Flight Carbon Calculator: https://www.atmosfair.de/en/offset/flight/							
		kg CO2e per SEAT	kg CO2e/pKM				
Average AirlinePer passenger FLIGHT ECONOMY Ottawa to Toronto [Assuming average loads AND Radiative Forcing @412km]		78	0.189	Yes	No	No	No
Average AirlinePer passenger FLIGHT ECONOMY Ottawa to Montreal [Assuming average loads AND Radiative Forcing @201km]		27	0.134	Yes	No	No	No
Rail and Flight Emissions Factors in Canada, according to Katz-Rosene: DOI: 10.1111/cag.12649							
		kg CO2e per SEAT	kg CO2e/pKM				
Rail emissions within the Quebec-Windsor Corridor Per Seat Windsor to Quebec City [1169km] - 100% Load ECONOMY		35.95	0.031	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Rail emissions within the Quebec-Windsor Corridor Per Seat Windsor to Quebec City [1169km] - 57% Load ECONOMY		63.07	0.054	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Flight emissions per seat within the Quebec Windsor Corridor [1046km] ECONOMY - average of 'high' and 'low' est		189	0.181	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Rail emissions Factor Ocean (Monton to Montreal) 1094km ECONOMY - Load Factor included			0.96	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Rail emissions Factor 'The Canadian' (Toronto to Vancouver) ECONOMY - Load Factor included			0.162	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Flight emissions per seat Toronto to Vancouver using Atmosfair [3349km] ECONOMY - average of 'high' and 'low' est		615.5	0.184	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Flight emissions per seat Montreal to Halifax using Atmosfair [805km] ECONOMY - average of 'high' and 'low' est		172.5	0.214	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Comparators to High-Speed Rail in the Toronto-Montreal line according to Bien et al. https://munkschool.utoronto.ca/media/1560/download							
Existing Via Rail service emissions per seat (Unstated Load Factor) @540km		14.76	0.027	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
Air Travel [Unstated Load Factor] @507km		83	0.164	Yes	No	No	No
Car [Unstated occupancy] @540km - excluded due to lack of data on load factor		33.88	0.063	No	No	No	No
International Transport Emissions Factors from IEA https://www.iea.org/data-and-statistics/charts/ghg-intensity-of-passenger-transport-modes-2019							
Well-to-wheels global averages per passenger, excluding non-CO2 climate forcings	grams CO2/pKM	kg CO2/pKM	kg CO2e/pKM				
Rail Global Average - Non-Urban	14	0.014	0.014	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Buses and Minibuses - Non-Urban	22	0.022	0.022	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Small and Medium Cars - Non-Urban - Assumed 1 passenger	91	0.091	0.091	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Large Cars - Non-Urban - Assumed 1 passenger	132	0.132	0.132	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Air	144	0.144	0.144	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
International Flight Emissions - Atmosfair - One Way Economy: https://www.atmosfair.de/en/offset/flight/							
	Flight Distance (km)	kg CO2e per SEAT	kg CO2e/pKM				
Ottawa to Los Angeles - Economy - Average Airline	3875	789	0.204	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Ottawa to Amsterdam, Netherlands - Economy - Average Airline	5688	1298	0.228	No	No	Yes	Yes
Ottawa to Bangkok, Thailand - Economy - Average Airline	13501	4021	0.298	No	No	Yes	Yes
Ottawa to Johannesburg, South Africa - Economy - Average Airline	13154	3882	0.295	No	No	Yes	Yes
Ottawa to Quito, Ecuador - Economy - Average Airline	5117	1134	0.222	No	No	Yes	Yes

REDUCING OUR TRAVEL FOOTPRINT - BACKGROUND RESEARCH DOCUMENT

Electric Vehicle Emissions Factors Comparison in Canada: <https://www.cer-rec.gc.ca/en/data-analysis/energy-markets/market-snapshots/2018/market-snapshot-how-much-co2-do-electric-vehicles-hybrids-gasoline-vehicles-emit.html>

	gramsCO2e/ vehicle km	kg CO2e/pkm			
Ontario					
Small EV in Ontario - 1 passenger - Hyundai Ioniq	6.2	0.006	Yes	Yes	Yes
Small PLUG-IN Hybrid in Ontario - 1 passenger - Toyota Prius Prime	6.2	0.006	Yes	Yes	Yes
Small NON-plug Hybrid in Ontario - 1 passenger - Toyota Prius Eco	96.2	0.096	Yes	Yes	Yes
Small ICE in Ontario - 1 passenger - Honda Civic	149.6	0.150	Yes	Yes	Yes
Large PLUG-IN Hybrid in Ontario - 1 passenger Volvo XC90	12.4	0.012	Yes	Yes	Yes
Large NON-plug Hybrid in Ontario - 1 passenger Toyota Highlander Hybrid	185.7	0.186	Yes	Yes	Yes
Large ICE in Ontario - 1 passenger - Dodge Grand Caravan	269.3	0.269	Yes	Yes	Yes
Small EV in Ontario - 4 passenger - Hyundai Ioniq	6.2	0.002	Yes	Yes	Yes
Small PLUG-IN Hybrid in Ontario - 4 passenger - Toyota Prius Prime	6.2	0.002	Yes	Yes	Yes
Small NON-plug Hybrid in Ontario - 4 passenger - Toyota Prius Eco	96.2	0.024	Yes	Yes	Yes
Small ICE in Ontario - 4 passenger - Honda Civic	149.6	0.037	Yes	Yes	Yes
Large PLUG-IN Hybrid in Ontario - 4 passenger Volvo XC90	12.4	0.003	Yes	Yes	Yes
Large NON-plug Hybrid in Ontario - 4 passenger Toyota Highlander Hybrid	185.7	0.046	Yes	Yes	Yes
Large ICE in Ontario - 4 passenger - Dodge Grand Caravan	269.3	0.067	Yes	Yes	Yes
Quebec					
Small EV in Quebec - 1 passenger - Hyundai Ioniq	0.3	0.000	Yes	Yes	Yes
Small PLUG-IN Hybrid in Quebec - 1 passenger - Toyota Prius Prime	0.3	0.000	Yes	Yes	Yes
Small NON-plug Hybrid in Quebec - 1 passenger - Toyota Prius Eco	96.2	0.096	Yes	Yes	Yes
Small ICE in Quebec - 1 passenger - Honda Civic	149.6	0.150	Yes	Yes	Yes
Large PLUG-IN Hybrid in Quebec - 1 passenger Volvo XC90	0.5	0.001	Yes	Yes	Yes
Large NON-plug Hybrid in Quebec - 1 passenger Toyota Highlander Hybrid	185.7	0.186	Yes	Yes	Yes
Large ICE in Quebec - 1 passenger - Dodge Grand Caravan	269.3	0.269	Yes	Yes	Yes
Small EV in Quebec - 4 passenger - Hyundai Ioniq	0.3	0.000	Yes	Yes	Yes
Small PLUG-IN Hybrid in Quebec - 4 passenger - Toyota Prius Prime	0.3	0.000	Yes	Yes	Yes
Small NON-plug Hybrid in Quebec - 4 passenger - Toyota Prius Eco	96.2	0.024	Yes	Yes	Yes
Small ICE in Quebec - 4 passenger - Honda Civic	149.6	0.037	Yes	Yes	Yes
Large PLUG-IN Hybrid in Quebec - 4 passenger Volvo XC90	0.5	0.000	Yes	Yes	Yes
Large NON-plug Hybrid in Quebec - 4 passenger Toyota Highlander Hybrid	185.7	0.046	Yes	Yes	Yes
Large ICE in Quebec - 4 passenger - Dodge Grand Caravan	269.3	0.067	Yes	Yes	Yes
Fossil Fuel Grid (Alberta)					
Small EV in Alberta - 1 passenger - Hyundai Ioniq	139.8	0.140	No	Yes	Yes
Small PLUG-IN Hybrid in Alberta - 1 passenger - Toyota Prius Prime	139.8	0.140	No	Yes	Yes
Small NON-plug Hybrid in Alberta - 1 passenger - Toyota Prius Eco	96.2	0.096	No	Yes	Yes
Small ICE in Alberta - 1 passenger - Honda Civic	149.6	0.150	No	Yes	Yes
Large PLUG-IN Hybrid in Alberta - 1 passenger Volvo XC90	279.6	0.280	No	Yes	Yes
Large NON-plug Hybrid in Alberta - 1 passenger Toyota Highlander Hybrid	185.7	0.186	No	Yes	Yes
Large ICE in Alberta - 1 passenger - Dodge Grand Caravan	269.3	0.269	No	Yes	Yes
Small EV in Alberta - 4 passenger - Hyundai Ioniq	139.8	0.035	No	Yes	Yes
Small PLUG-IN Hybrid in Alberta - 4 passenger - Toyota Prius Prime	139.8	0.035	No	Yes	Yes
Small NON-plug Hybrid in Alberta - 4 passenger - Toyota Prius Eco	96.2	0.024	No	Yes	Yes
Small ICE in Alberta - 4 passenger - Honda Civic	149.6	0.037	No	Yes	Yes
Large PLUG-IN Hybrid in Alberta - 4 passenger Volvo XC90	279.6	0.070	No	Yes	Yes
Large NON-plug Hybrid in Alberta - 4 passenger Toyota Highlander Hybrid	185.7	0.046	No	Yes	Yes
Large ICE in Alberta - 4 passenger - Dodge Grand Caravan	269.3	0.067	No	Yes	Yes

APPENDIX B: uOttawa emissions related to travel (2015-2020)

Disclaimer: The data presented is strictly for information purposes only. It is based on information from the aviation industry and other sources. Whilst every care has been taken in preparing the content of the report to avoid errors, the Authors make no warranty as to the accuracy, completeness or currency of the content. The Authors shall not be liable for any kind of damages or other claims or demands incurred as a result of incorrect, insufficient or invalid data, or arising out of or in connection with the use, copying or display of the content. The information contained in the report should not be construed as legal advice.